

Myth Versus Realism : A Critical Study of 'Draupadi' in Chitra B. Divakaruni's *The Palace of Illusions* and in Mahasweta Devi's *Breast Stories / Draupadi*

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Abstract

In the great epics of the Vedic period, *The Ramayana* and *The Mahabharata*, the identity and functions of the queen and other royal women were determined by the stiff patriarchal norms. These mythical royal women, whether the subdued Sita or the fiery Draupadi, had to undergo traditional patriarchal norm of subjugation without any complain from their side. Recently, due to the trends of radical feminism, some of the feminist novelists like Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni, Mahasweta Devi, Shashi Deshpande and others have tried to explore the reality of these mythical female characters by placing them at the forefront of the patriarchal society. One of such mythical female characters is Draupadi whose existential dilemma has been studied both from the male and the female point of views. This research paper intends to explain the fictional art of both Divakaruni and Devi who have articulated an independent, free voice for Draupadi in their novels or stories, *The Palace of Illusions* and *Breast Stories/Draupadi* respectively.

Keywords

Mythical Characters, Patriarchal Norm, Subjugation, Existential Dilemma, Traditional, Radical Feminism.

Introduction

There is no doubt about the prevalent social custom, which has been followed from the days of yore, that the dignity and identity of a woman is determined by the male members of the family or by the Patriarchal norms. A woman can't maintain her separate identity, without adjusting herself and showing her relationship with one or two male members of the family. Still in modern times, this kind of social imposition, as an ethical norm of society, holds good both in high and low societies. Even we worship our powerful goddesses, only by placing them by the side of their male counterparts. In the great epics of the vedic period, *The Ramayana* and *The Mahabharata*, we get the same patriarchal norms, applying upon the queens and other royal women, to determine their identity and functions. These mythical royal women, whether the subdued, dutiful Sita, as the wife of Lord Rama or the fiery Draupadi, the humiliated wife of the Pandavas, had to undergo traditional patriarchal norm of subjugation without any complain from their side. Recently, due to the trends of radical feminism, some of the feminist novelists, like Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni, Shashi Deshpande, Mahasweta Devi and others have tried to explore the reality of these mythical female characters by placing them at the forefront of the Patriarchal society. One of such mythical female characters of the Indian epics is Draupadi whose character has been studied by the feminist writers both from the male and the female point of views. The phallogocentric image of a mythic female character seems to be created strictly with the patriarchal image and dictates whereas the Gynocentric studies exposes the reality, the suppressed spiritual beauty and identity of the stereotyped gendered subalterns, like Sita and Draupadi. To support these Gynocentric studies of mythical characters, Helen Cixous states: "when 'the repressed' of their culture and their society returns, it's an explosive, utterly destructive, staggering return".(1)

To realize the expectations of the feminist critics, both Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni and Mahasweta Devi have tried to reinterpret the mythical, stereotyped character of Draupadi their novels, *The Palace of Illusions* (2008) and *Breast Stories* (2018) respectively. The rational studies of the mythical Draupadi by Divakaruni and by Devi reveal her own inner strength and identity which subvert her long-perceived image from a subdued woman to an independent woman of free-will. This research paper intends to explain the fictional art and credentials of both Divakaruni and Devi who have articulated a new, free feminine voice for such a silent, mythical female figure of yore, Draupadi. This paper would analyse first the independent, confessing Draupadi of Divakaruni and then it would reveal the hidden courage of Devi's 'Dopdi' which puts the arrogant Masculinity in shame.

Objective of study

This paper would analyse first the independent, confessing Draupadi of Divakaruni and then it would reveal the hidden courage of Devi's 'Dopdi' which puts the arrogant Masculinity in shame.

Review of Literature

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Main Text

In her much-acclaimed novel, *The Palace of Illusions*, Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni has recast the main events of *The Mahabharata*, leading to the devastating war of Kurukshetra, from the feminine point of view or through the speculative voice of Panchali or Draupadi. Draupadi evaluates her role and worth as a daughter, wife, mother and loving friend, and tries to discover her own self-esteem as an individual. In this context, Divakaruni says that she has been not satisfied with the conventional, mythical stories of the female characters of *The Mahabharata* because their worth is judged only through their role in the defeat and victory of their male relatives, whether they are fathers or brothers or husbands. Her curious, independent female self wants to hear their journeys, from the world of innocence to that of experience, through their own mouth, based exclusively on their personal experiences. For this purpose, Divakaruni has selected the most controversial female character of *The Mahabharata*, named Panchali or Draupadi : "It is her life, her voice, her questions and her visions that I invite you in *The Palace of Illusions*(2). Actually, Divakaruni depicts Panchali, a character suffering from her existential dilemma, who wants to liberate herself from the Patriarchal relationship-oriented identity. It is only through the spiritual love and emotional support of lord Krishna that Panchali or Draupadi comes out victorious through the Patriarchal coils of relationships.

Panchali or Draupadi recalls her birth, along with her brother, Dhristadyumna during the worship of holy fire at his father's palace; she suppresses her grief as a female child when her father, Drupad, rejected her initially. However, she overcomes that humiliating grief when her brother acknowledges her as his own inseparable, worthy sister. Lord Krishna calls her *Sakhi* for having a dusky complexion and tries to instil a sense of confidence for ignoring her dark skin. From this point onwards, Lord Krishna becomes her spiritual strength, her soul-mate who remains seated in the recesses of her being. As the representative of the bold women, she rejects the derogatory belief, "women were the root of all the world's troubles." (3) and does not want only to be a second in all daring events of her Patriarchal family. Draupadi expresses her resentment against her position of being the wife of five pandavas, and says that she has been denied her freedom of choice on marital affairs and has been used as "a communal drinking cup", which remains passing "from hand to hand". (4) Nevertheless, she adjusts her status of being a wife of five men , for which she has been ridiculed in the Assembly hall by the Kauravas, the fierce opponents of the Pandavas.

Draupadi or Panchali feels the moments of pride and social security when she has been installed as the sole mistress or queen of her magical palace, especially built for her by her husbands, which she likes to call, "the Palace of Illusions". Her own inflated ego leads the destruction of her illusionary palace and her happy married life. While following the footprints of her husband, Yudhishthir to his final journey to *Mahaprasthan*, Panchali realizes her love divided between her lawful husbands and Karna whom she had rejected as her suitor due to his low birth, though she had a kind of romantic yearning for him. After losing her sons and almost all male relatives in the historic war of Kurukshetra, Panchali tries to redeem her guilty self by helping the innocent, helpless war - widows in rehabilitating themselves fearlessly through trade and other domestic arts. When the Mahabharata war was going on, Panchali realizes her own guilt and the real character of Patriarchy through her physical and spiritual eyesight, gifted to her by the sage Vyasa. She regrets for the nobility and loyalty of Karna and "his uncomplaining acceptance of the injustice of his life, his forgiveness" (5). While recalling all her past moments of anger, grief, lust and pride , caused mainly by her relationship with various male members in various capacity, Panchali gets disenchanted with her illusionary physical life of pomp and prestige and finds that during all those phases or roles of her existence , she didn't experience the completeness of life or the reality of her existence. The layers of her life as daughter, wife, mother and queen constitute her existence as illusionary as her palace of illusions which became the chief cause of such a catastroph war as Kurukshetra.

The karma- yoga sermon , based on compassion and righteousness, delivered by Lord Krishna - to Arjuna , finally liberates her enslaved physical identity to an infinite cosmic one. Her soul and body , chained in various roles, given to her by patriarchy, gets merged with the spiritual part of Lord Krishna , her *Sakhi* , her saviour : "she becomes buoyant and expansive and uncontainable"... beyond name, gender and the imprisoning patterns of ego"(6)

Devakaruni narrates Draupadi' or panchali's tale of spiritual Strength, resilience and enlightenment through her own autobiographical style which ultimately creates her image as infinite and timeless as Krishna himself. The re-interpretation of *The Mahabharata*, through the feminist mind of Draupadi or Panchali, challenges several norms of Patriarchy as illusionary and hypocritical for the sole purpose of Keeping the women in the margin.

If Divakaruni gives the independent voice to the mute and abused queen of the Pandavas, Devi depicts her radical Draupadi, tearing out the coils of the man-made

feminine sexuality which has been directly related to the female body. *Draupadi* is one of the three short stories, written by Mahasweta Devi which are collected in a volume, entitled *Breast Stories*. Devi's story *Draupadi* is, out and out, realistic in tone and presentation since it represents a new female-oriented insurgent writing which encourages the feminist writes to subvert the stereotyped or mythical female identities and gestures as a matter of resistance to the Patriarchy. Dopdi Mejhen, the tribal female Naxalite, is introduced as the most wanted, notorious female militant who is charged with the murder of the landlord, Surja Sahu. Moreover, Dopdi Mejhen is also accused of helping the other hard-core Naxalites in their hide-outs. She keeps on dodging the police to escape her arrest and custody-torture list she should divulge the secrets of her Naxalite brethren.

Both Dopdi and her husband, Dulna Majhi were maintaining their revolutionary, Naxalite game of kill-and-hide successfully when Dulna was shot dead with the bullet of the Indian Army, led by the gentleman Senanayak. Mr. Senanayak had read about these harvest workers-turned-Naxalites and their guerrilla warfare, but he had no practical and first-hand or experiences of their real existence and problems in the hilly surroundings of Jharkani. As a committed activist of the Naxalite groups, Dopdi abandons the dead body of her loving husband, Dulna only to allude the Army's trap, but finally she is captured and dragged to the military camp for interrogation. After confronting with the tough, vindictive self of Dopdi, the decent, civilized Senanayak orders his soldiers, "Make her do the needful"(7) for having all required informations related to Naxalites and their proposed rebellious activities. This military order of the Senanayak makes the female body of Dopdi as a passive object for the brutal sexual assault, made by the Indian soldiers whose male bodies are nurtured with the government's fund for protecting domestic norms and other human rights. The feminine body of Dopdi has been raped again and again, but she doesn't divulge any secret or cry for mercy.

At Dawn, Dopdi is asked to cover her stark-naked body with her clothes so that she may present herself before the decent Senanayak as a timid female body with all her feminine grace. Dopdi laughs at the false patriarchal norms of feminine grace and modesty and moves forward with her naked, sexually-ravaged body to the camp of the Senanayak. The fierce, immodest feminine figure of Dopdi, without having a single piece of clothes on her sexually-vulnerable body, challenges the masculinity of Senanayak and his soldiers because they have never confronted the daring, naked female body, challenging them to cover her body for the restoration of female modesty and grace. Senanayak and his soldiers feel defeated by the radical feminism of a naked black female body. Unlike her mythical namesake of *The Mahabharata*, Dopdi refuses to call any male saviour, like lord Krishna, to protect her female body from the sexual assault of the power-drunk, arrogant patriarchy. She flouts the old mythical image of a pleading Draupadi in favour of her female modesty; Instead, she rejects her clothes as the weak gesture of female modesty since it provokes the masculinity of the patriarchy. Dopdi's "anti-sexual boldness terrified even the most skillful Senanayak" and in such a situation, "she is thereby empowered to become goddess"(8).

Devi has skilfully named the tribal militant woman as Dopdi, a derivative of "Draupadi" because her defiant naked body has exploded the ages-old myth of an exploited, abused female body, appealing before her own male relatives to be her saviour. It is really ironical to know that the actual name of Dopdi was "Draupadi" given to her by the wife of Surja Sahu for whom her mother had been working, but this high-class Sanskrit name gets perverted as "Dopdi" by the unrefined, low-class tongue of the tribals. Devi's Dopdi also ridicules the aggressive masculine system of rape to control and subjugate the female body which makes a woman too defiled a person to command social dignity. Devi tries to expose the stereotyped or prejudicial rape myths, established and perpetuated by the insensitive patriarchy. Supporting the feminist stance of Mahasweta Devi, Lonsway and Fitzgerald also denounce rape myths as "attitudes and beliefs that are generally false but are widely and persistently held, and that serve to deny and justify male sexual aggression against women" (9). The Marxist - Feminist writes like Mahasweta Devi and her English translator, Gayatri Spivak Chakravorty are not ready to accept the mythic image of Draupadi as a sexually-fragile body, but a defiant, anti- sexual female body challenging the patriarchal norms of rape or sexual assaults.

The myth and realism, lying behind the enigmatic feminine character of *The Mahabharata's* Draupadi cannot be summed up without adding the viewpoints of another modern feminist writer, Shashi Deshpande. According to Shashi Deshpande, the image or so-called facts are already implanted in our mind before we start reading the psychology and physical identity of any mythical character. Myths are so imposing, and forceful that our mind dare not to create any independent image of a mythical or legendary character, especially in the case of female characters. Actually, their characters become the social - patriarchal trends or conventions. That's why, Deshpande says that even our self- image is supported by this baggage of myth since "they are part of the human psyche, part of our cultural histories" (10). In her famous short story, "And what Has Been Decided?", Shashi Deshpande makes her Draupadi express her long - subdued dilemma, related to her renowned marital status with the five pandavas and her humiliations as a vulnerable female body during the game of dice in the Assembly Hall of Hastinapur. She has to follow the long - ruling myth of femininity which seems to her the unjust demand of the male - dominated society. Even though she belongs to the five most powerful warriors, yet she has been looked upon only as an object to be possessed and enjoyed. She realizes her reality, just as a mute object when she has been wagered by her husband,

Yudhishtir, the custodian of *dharma* in the game of dice. A disillusioned Draupadi asks: "what is this *Dharma*? ... where do I fit into all these games of yours."(11)

Still in modern days, the revolutionary, feminist attitude of Writers tries to solve these ever-haunting mythical images of subdued femininity.

Conclusion

The existential dilemma, humiliations, sufferings and salvation of Draupadi, the wife of the Pandavas, invites the intellectual attention of the feminist writers like Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni, Mahasweta Devi, Shashi Deshpande and other feminist writers. As Deshpande confesses, she has been motivated to explore the injured female psyche of Draupadi through her reading of Iravati Karve's *Yuganta* in which the mythical characters of *The Mahabharata* are studied by repositioning in the modern, liberal perspective. Through their open-ended re-examination of Draupadi's character, both Divakaruni and Devi reject the hollow, conventional concept of 'femininity', or "the ideals of female body" as established by Patriarchy to satisfy their male-chauvinism. In their fictional recreation of Draupadi in *The Palace of Illusions* and *Dopdi in Draupadi* by Divakaruni and Devi respectively, we find a new, liberated incarnation of the mythical Draupadi which must be admired as the image of 'a New woman', free from the coils of gendered subalternism.

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